

Research Brief

Lived experience of parents of children with Hydrocephalus in a Tertiary Hospital, Kerala.

Nidhin Elias, Anila K.P, Sivani R, Sneha R, Sona Mary Vinod, Sreedevi P, Sanal kumar
Amrita College of Nursing, Amrita Vishwa Vidyapeetham, Kochi, Kerala, India.

Objective: To explore the lived experiences of parents of children with hydrocephalus, assess their knowledge of shunt management and complications, and examine challenges in their social life.

Methods: A phenomenological qualitative study was conducted with twelve parents of children (<12 years) diagnosed with hydrocephalus, using convenience sampling. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews and its analyzed with thematic approach.

Results: Under the experience of parents of children with hydrocephalus, The analysis of parental accounts revealed four overarching themes: Uncertainty (sub theme-*Reaction to the Child's Diagnosis, Concerns About the Disorder and Treatment Modalities, and Concerns About the Child's Future*), Developing Expertise (sub theme-*aking Sense of Hydrocephalus and Shunt Surgery and Complications.*), Social and Family Life (sub theme-*Barriers to Normal Family Life and Barriers to Social Life*), and Difficulties During and After Treatment (Sub theme-*Financial Instability and Infection Prevention*). Parents initially experienced fear and confusion but gradually developed expertise in recognizing complications, particularly shunt malfunction and infection. The condition significantly affected their psychological well-being and social functioning. Adaptive strategies evolved over time to manage ongoing challenges.

Conclusion: Parents play a crucial role in early identification and ongoing care of child illness period. This study evidenced that, empowering parents through education and psycho-social support is essential for improving child outcomes and parental coping.

Keywords: Hydrocephalus, parents' experience, shunts, caregiver burden.

Cite This Paper

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Introduction

Hydrocephalus is a chronic neurological condition, primarily diagnosed in early childhood, characterized by the accumulation of excess cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) in the brain's ventricular system, leading to abnormal head enlargement and neurological complications ^[1]. It is not a singular disease but often occurs secondary to conditions such as neural tube defects (e.g., spina bifida), brain tumors, infections, hemorrhages, or trauma ^[2]. Medically, hydrocephalus is defined as a pathological distension of the ventricular system due to an imbalance between CSF production and absorption ^[3].

Hydrocephalus is among the most frequent pediatric neurological conditions requiring surgical intervention ^[4]. Infection, particularly meningitis, is the leading cause in many regions, accounting for over 60% of cases ^[5]. If untreated, the condition can result in significant disability, including blindness, deafness, and cognitive impairment ^[6]. The burden of caregiving becomes long-term and complex, affecting the physical, emotional, and economic well-being of families ^[7].

The mainstay of treatment is surgical, most commonly the placement of a ventriculoperitoneal (VP) shunt, which diverts CSF from the brain to another part of the body for reabsorption ^[8]. However, complications such as shunt malfunction and infection are common. Studies estimate that 40% of children require shunt revision within two years of placement ^[9], and nearly half of those discharged in good condition face recurrent blockages, seizures, or fever ^[8].

Cultural stigma and limited knowledge often hinder early diagnosis and treatment. Some caregivers perceive the condition as a curse, leading to social isolation and reluctance to seek medical care ^[10]. Given the multifaceted challenges faced by these families, this study aimed to explore and document parents' lived experiences caring for children with hydrocephalus.

Materials and Methods

A qualitative, descriptive phenomenological approach was adopted to explore the lived experiences of parents. The study was conducted at a tertiary care center in Kerala, India. The target population comprised parents of children aged below 12 years diagnosed with hydrocephalus.

Sampling

Twelve parents (participants saturated) were selected the children with hydrocephalus by convenient sampling and they consented to be part of study ,spoke local language and no mental disorder, considering inclusion and exclusion criteria related to the child's age, diagnosis, and hospitalization status^(10,11,12).

A participant consent information sheet prepared based on WHO qualitative ethics guideline. This consent format described the objective, willingness, commitment, discussion of conflict of ideas, and the confidentiality of the sharing experience. Next, the parents interview conducted according to their a convenient time . Interviews continued until saturation in data occurred, and it was deemed that no further information could be obtained and data collection became redundant ^[13].

Data Collection

Following ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board, consent was obtained from all participants. Data was collected using semi-structured, in-depth interviews with the help of a prepared guide, each lasting 20–40 minutes. Interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed verbatim. Followed the generation code (privacy); three researchers, each of whom thoroughly evaluated the content. And they identify different and similar codes and different levels of themes. At last, they named the themes, and researchers defined these themes⁽¹³⁾.

Data Tools

Tool 1 : Socio-demographic data questionnaire

The demographic profile contain data such as Name of the child, age of child and parent , birth order, family income , details about housing , vehicles, hospital expenditure, admission and surger details related to the sample .

Tool 2 : In-depth Interviewing questionnaire: Semi-structured interview guide.

A In- depth interview questionnaire to find out the life experience of living with the child with hydrocephalus and their everyday life during the past years .The in-depth interview was organised under 5 headings such as describing the experiences (7 questions) , knowledge of hydrocephalus (4 questions) , deciding illness symptom (2 questions) , feeling of impact of the hydrocephalus (12 questions) , concluding questions (2 questions) and other factors felt by the parents .

Results

The analysis of parental accounts revealed four overarching themes: Uncertainty, Developing Expertise, Social and Family Life, and Difficulties During and After Treatment. These themes were further categorized into related subthemes,

1. Uncertainty

Uncertainty permeated the experiences of parents from the moment of their child's diagnosis and continued through every stage of development. This theme included the subthemes: *Reaction to the Child's Diagnosis*, *Concerns About the Disorder and Treatment Modalities*, and *Concerns About the Child's Future*.

Reaction to the Child's Diagnosis

Parents commonly described the initial diagnosis as shocking and overwhelming. The lack of prior knowledge about hydrocephalus, coupled with the immediate need for surgical intervention, intensified their emotional distress.

“It was very difficult to accept, and all of a sudden I felt so blank. The scariest part as when they discussed the surgical procedure, and I asked several times if there was any way to avoid it.”

“My child was a preterm baby. At 39 days old, he had a seizure and was hospitalized, where he was diagnosed with meningitis. Hydrocephalus developed as a complication. I’ve had two tubal pregnancies before— I couldn’t bear to lose another child.”

Concerns About the Disorder and Treatment Modalities

The journey of understanding hydrocephalus was described as emotionally turbulent. Parents reported fluctuating levels of anxiety as they attempted to gather and interpret information, often from unfamiliar medical contexts or unreliable sources.

“I had little idea about the condition. I first consulted the doctor, then a family friend, and later turned to social media for information.”

“I had the foggiest idea about hydrocephalus and shunt procedures before my child was diagnosed. No one in my family or community had ever dealt with this.”

Concerns About the Child’s Future

Fears about long-term outcomes were pervasive. Parents worried about developmental milestones, social integration, and their child's ability to live independently. These concerns were particularly heightened for children with complex needs.

“Currently, my child does not show developmental delays, but the fear of whether he’ll live a normal life is one of my greatest concerns. I hope, by God’s grace, he will survive this.”

“My child hasn’t attained head control, and the doctors said it may be difficult for him. This terrifies me—what kind of future can he have?”

2. Developing Expertise

Over time, parents developed substantial knowledge and coping mechanisms to manage their child’s condition. This theme included two subthemes: *Making Sense of Hydrocephalus* and *Shunt Surgery and Complications*.

Making Sense of Hydrocephalus

Many parents had no prior understanding of hydrocephalus and described the diagnosis as confusing and emotionally overwhelming. They actively sought knowledge to better care for their child.

“The term hydrocephalus still seems difficult for me to digest. I just know it’s a condition where water accumulates in the brain.”

“The physician explained the condition, but as a housewife, I had very little understanding. The internet was my only source of information.”

Shunt Surgery and Complications

Parents expressed initial fear about brain surgery but gradually gained confidence through interactions with healthcare professionals and personal research. Many assumed the role of primary caregivers, especially for post-operative care and monitoring for complications.

“Initially, I understood it was a tube from the head to the stomach to reduce the fluid. I asked many questions and felt relieved after the doctor reassured me. That’s when I signed the consent.”

“After surgery, I resigned from my job to care for my child full-time. I knew it was important to monitor for complications and prevent infection.”

3. Social and Family Life

Raising a child with hydrocephalus profoundly impacted family dynamics and social interactions. This theme encompassed *Barriers to Normal Family Life* and *Barriers to Social Life*.

Barriers to Normal Family Life

Extended hospitalizations and the need for constant care disrupted family routines and responsibilities, often affecting other children and leading to emotional and logistical strain.

“We had about six months of hospital stays. It severely affected our daily life. I have a two-year-old son who had to stay with my parents. It was a very difficult period for our family.”

“Managing him after surgery required someone to always be there. I lost my job because of it.”

Barriers to Social Life

Parents described withdrawing from social activities out of fear of infection and due to the emotional burden. Job loss, social isolation, and a significant shift in lifestyle were common experiences.

“My wife lost her job and was permanently terminated from Saudi. This caused her depression. Now she’s under counselling. The whole family is struggling socially and emotionally.”

“We isolated ourselves from others. We couldn’t attend important family functions or travel, especially since my child was a preterm baby and post-surgery we feared infection constantly.”

4. Difficulties During and After Treatment

Parents reported significant difficulties related to both the treatment phase and long-term management. The two main subthemes were *Financial Instability* and *Infection Prevention*.

Financial Instability

The cost of treatment created serious economic burdens. Many families reported financial hardship that affected both ongoing care and overall family wellbeing.

“We are from a middle-class family and couldn’t manage the treatment expenses and long-term hospitalization.”

“After the treatment, we were economically drained. We had already spent a lot on infertility treatments before starting treatment for hydrocephalus.”

Infection Prevention

Infection control was a major concern for parents, particularly due to the risk of shunt-related complications. Many adopted strict hygiene practices and social restrictions to prevent infections.

“We used every possible method to prevent infections—limited contact with others, special soaps, and we restricted anyone else from handling the baby.”

“After the first VP shunt, my child developed a bacterial infection which turned into meningitis and sepsis. It was terrifying, and after that I became extremely strict about hygiene at home.”

Discussion

This study provides insight into the emotional, social, and practical challenges faced by parents caring for children with hydrocephalus. Findings align with earlier studies that reported initial emotional distress, especially upon diagnosis and during surgery^[11,12]. Similar to Kulkarni et al., the current study found that over time, parents gain knowledge and confidence, becoming adept at recognizing shunt malfunctions and managing post-operative care^[14].

Despite increasing competence, persistent psychological stress remains due to the unpredictability of complications and uncertainty about the child’s future^[15]. Parents continue to face long-term emotional challenges, even as they adapt to the caregiving role.

Moreover, our findings reaffirm that knowledge acquisition is often self-initiated, through internet resources or peer support. As Oyewole et al. suggested, formal caregiver education programs could enhance preparedness and reduce anxiety^[16].

The study also highlights the social consequences of caregiving, including occupational sacrifices, emotional strain, and reduced participation in social life, consistent with prior findings^[17,18]. Cultural perceptions and stigma contribute to social withdrawal, as seen in other Indian and global contexts^[10].

Importantly, many parents reported religious faith, family support, and counseling as key coping mechanisms—factors echoed in other literature as buffers against caregiver burnout^[19,20].

Conclusion

Parents of children with hydrocephalus endure a complex journey marked by emotional upheaval, the development of caregiving expertise, and significant socio-economic challenges. Despite achieving a degree of resilience and knowledge, they require ongoing support from health systems, especially through structured education, psychosocial counseling, and community outreach.

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